

INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR WATER COLLECTORS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to increasing the efficiency of solar-water collectors that heat water using solar energy. Light-absorbing elements of solar-water collectors have been proposed, constructive schemes have been developed. Based on the developed constructive scheme, the mode of operation of the solar-water collector is studied.

Keywords: solar-water collector, solar energy, light-returning element, solar radiation current, radiation surface, collector pipes.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СОЛНЕЧНЫХ ВОДОСБОРНИКОВ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена повышению эффективности гелио-водяных коллекторов, нагревающих воду за счет солнечной энергии. Предложены светопоглощающие элементы гелиоколлекторов, разработаны конструктивные схемы. На основе разработанной конструктивной схемы изучен режим работы гелиоколлектора.

Ключевые слова: гелио-водяной коллектор, солнечная энергия, световозвращающий элемент, ток солнечного излучения, поверхность излучения, коллекторные трубы.

INTRODUCTION

By the 21st century of technology, the conditions were created for the development of modern and most effective devices for using “renewable energy sources”. This will primarily help prevent the release of harmful substances into ecology and thus save non-renewable energy sources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Currently, 80% of the energy consumed is obtained from activated coal, oil, gases from non-renewable energy sources, the so-called natural fuels. Now, practical work is underway to replace our need for this energy with renewable energy sources.

The transformation of solar energy into thermal energy occurs at the expense of the ability of the atoms of matter to absorb electromagnetic radiation. In this case, the energy of electromagnetic radiation is converted into the kinetic energy of the atoms and molecules of the substance, that is, into thermal energy. As a result, the temperature of the substance rises. Obtaining heat in such a method, due to its simplicity, provides an opportunity to achieve an adequate supply of energy to consumers of different levels. This path allows us to collect energy using environmentally friendly solar energy.

RESULTS

The principle of operation of solar thermal devices is based on the absorption of solar radiation by a black surface that receives solar radiation. This process can be quite complicated

depending on the type of light-absorbing material. Thanks to this, the energy of radiation at all wavelengths changes to heat. In this we will mainly consider the solar-water collector (Photo 1). We carry out this by placing additional equipment on the Collector part, which is the main part of the device to feed more energy. By providing full sunlight to the surfaces of the Collector pipes, we achieve a more complete absorption of energy. Water solar collectors were developed with light-returning elements even earlier. But in these structural elements, the beam-returning element is made several tens of times larger than the Collector pipe.

Figure 1.

Scheme and appearance of the solar-water collector.

a) solar collector Scheme, b) general view of the solar-water collector.

An example of this includes collectors made with parabolas, flat, conical and several other structural elements (fig. In this case, the amount of energy that the Collector absorbs will be bound to the Collector's absorption coefficient, the return coefficient of the mirror, the radiation surface and radiation shell, the diameter of the Collector pipes, the average radiation of the mirror, and several other structural elements.

Figure 2.

a) parabolic, b) parabolic with secondary reflector, d) Frenel concentrator

Figure 3.

Proposed collector structure.

DISCUSSION

The difference between this and the previous light-returning elements in aqueous solar collectors is that we take this light-returning element in one ratio with the Collector pipes and direct the pipe surface to the opposite side of the sun by direct orientation (fig.

CONCLUSION

This allows the aqueous solar collector to absorb heat through the full surfaces of its pipes. In this process, the light-returning element (mirror) allows the level of solar radiation to absorb solar radiation from the surface of the Collector pipe on the opposite side to the sun. As a result, by absorbing solar radiation through the full surface of the pipeline, we create the basis for increasing energy efficiency.

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